

An examination of different strategies to retrieve digital humanities publications from large-scale scientific databases

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Introduction

As a field emerged between humanities and contemporary information technologies, digital humanities (DH) has received increasing scholarly attention during the past decade (Jones, 2013). In particular, it is an important example of interdisciplinary field in the contexts of quantitative and qualitative science studies (Luhmann & Burghardt, 2022; Ma & Li, 2022).

Despite its growing importance in the research landscape, there is only a limited body of empirical works on DH using large-scale datasets. Besides the limited coverage of DH publications in major commercial scientific databases (Spinaci et al., 2022), the above limitation is due to the difficulties to operationalize the definition of DH into the query phrases to collect a representative sample of publications from the databases. Two strategies are commonly used: by a list of representative keywords and by core journals. Many empirical research on DH relies on one of these strategies (Su et al., 2020; Wang, 2018); however, the effectiveness of such strategies when used alone and their impacts on the empirical results have not been fully evaluated.

To fill the above gap, the present research project aims to compare DH journal publications acquired from journal match and keyword search, as an important step towards establishing a larger and potentially more comprehensive DH journal publication sample. This poster presents preliminary findings from our project, focusing on the comparison of the two subsamples in terms of (1) temporal distribution of publications, and (2) disciplinarity of publications. The implications of our preliminary findings and the next steps of our project are discussed in the end of the poster.

Data and Methods

In this research, we collected two samples of DH publications from the Dimensions database (version:

June 2022) housed in the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University. We did so by using the above two strategies: (1) identifying all publications from the core DH journals compiled by Spinaci et al. (2022) (i.e., *Journal* sample), and (2) searching the keywords of “digital humanities” and “digital humanity” in the textual columns of the bibliographic records, including the title, abstract, and concepts extracted by Dimensions (*Keyword* sample). From all downloaded publications, we limited our sample to (1) English-language research articles (2) that are published before the year of 2022.

To examine the disciplinarity of publications, we used the paper-level classification automatically assigned by the Dimensions database using a machine-learning approach (Herzog & Lunn, 2018). Their scheme uses the 22 Fields of Research (FOR) from the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC). One article can be assigned to multiple categories; as a result, we used the fractional counting method to understand how the publications are distributed across knowledge domains.

Results

Our final sample contains 4,774 publications that meet the above criteria, including 3,130 from core journals and 1,875 from keyword search. It should be noted that there are 231 publications covered by both samples. They are counted as a separate *Overlap* sample, so that we can make more direct comparisons between the two sources. The final publication counts of the three samples are 2,899 (*Journal*), 1,644 (*Keyword*), and 231 (*Overlap*), respectively. Figure 1 shows the temporal distributions of the three samples. It demonstrates a similarly increasing trend across the three samples since the late 2000s. However, the umbrella terms (“digital humanities” and “digital humanity”) only

emerged in the 2010s to capture the work practices of the field. Despite the increasing usage of these umbrella terms since 2010s, the actual DH practices remained diverse, and the diversity has increased during recent years with engagement from researchers from various domains (Poole, 2016).

Figure 1. Temporal distributions of the three subsamples of DH publications

We further examined how the three subsamples are distributed across the 22 knowledge domains defined in ANZSRC. In our total sample, only 3,475 (72.8%) of all publications have classification information, which are used in this analysis. Table 1 summarizes how the top six categories (all categories exceeding 2% in the overall sample) are used in our overall sample as well as in the two major subsamples. Despite the similar pattern among the three samples, the *Keyword* sample has more publications from humanities domains (especially *Language, Communication and Culture* and *History and Archaeology*), whereas the *Journal* sample is more closely connected to *Information and Computing Sciences* and *Philosophy and Religious Studies*. On top of the different orientations of DH publications from the two sources, this finding suggests that humanities researchers, especially those in areas of language and literary studies, are more receptive to using the term “digital humanities” directly to capture and conceptualize their work compared with researchers from other domains. This can be potentially attributed to the historic connections between DH and these fields.

Table 1. Distribution of subsamples over top six knowledge domains (ICS: Information and Computing Sciences; LCC: Language, Communication and Culture; PR: Philosophy and Religious Studies; HA: History and Archaeology; PCS: Psychology and Cognitive Sciences; SHS: Studies in Human Society)

Domain	% All	% Journal	% Keyword
ICS	31.5%	34.7%	26.5%
LCC	29.1%	26.2%	31.5%
PR	12.3%	19.2%	3.4%
HA	11.3%	8.3%	16.6%

PCS	5.0%	7.4%	1.6%
SHS	3.6%	1.8%	6.1%
Others	7.2%	2.4%	14.3%

Conclusion

This poster presents preliminary findings from our project aiming to understand how the selection of query strategies could impact empirical findings based on DH journal publication. Our preliminary findings suggest that despite the consistent growth of DH journal publications in both venues, the two sources have very little overlap, indicating that any single strategy may not guarantee a sample that is representative of the whole field of DH. More significantly, publications from the two sources have different disciplinary orientations, which may create biases to empirical findings based on them.

As the next step of this project, we aim to expand existing efforts, particularly to systematically evaluate the disciplinarity of publications from the two venues by investigating the domain of citing and cited documents as well as author-level knowledge domains. Moreover, another aspect of the analysis is the collaboration pattern of DH publications. These analyses will help us better understand the conditions of knowledge production in DH. We will also rely on such knowledge to construct a more comprehensive journal publication sample to conduct larger-scale analyses in the future.

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